

Adaptable Talents of Dr. Ursula Franklin

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V.X.Jeba Christy

*Assistant Professor and Head of the Department of Physics
Madonna Arts and Science College for Women, Madurai*

Abstract

In the world every human have their own talents, given by the God. People utilize that talents and made well-known name. Dr. Ursula Franklin is one among them. Her contribution is very important in science and technology. She was the first ‘University Professor’ in Toronto University. She published more than hundred papers and many books. She worked as a pacifist, feminist and Quaker to bring intense change in the society and world. She earned great awards and honors from different universities including “Pearson Peace Medal”. People should follow this multitaled person with her dedication. The way she approached the things defined her ‘Adaptable Talents’.

Introduction

Talents are the God’s gift to human. Everybody got the gift from God. Many people don’t know their original talent; they simply live the life without creating much impact on the society. But only a few people used that talents and became famous. Dr. Ursula Franklin comes under that category because of her adroit talents. People know her as a physicist and activist who acts to bring social change. Dr. Ursula says

“War does not work; not even for the warriors”

This line describes her as a thoughtful speaker. Here Dr. Ursula Franklin’s adaptable talents are going to expose in deep manner.

Babyhood

Dr. Ursula Rise in Munich, Germany on 16, September 1921. Her original name is Ursula Maria Martius. Her mother Ilse Maria Martius was a jewish and an art historian. The work of art historian is to study the objects of art includes painting, sculpture, architecture, ceramics and furniture. And her father Albrecht Martius was a lutharen and an ethnographer who study the culture of group of people. Albrecht came from old protestant family. An only child Ursula was raised in the protestant faith.

She shifted to Berlin in 1940 to begin her undergraduate studies in science. But that didn’t happen. Because of her mother’s Jewish background, she was imprisoned in Nazi labor camp in 1943. She herself spent 18 months in different camps and repaired bombed and damaged buildings. At that time, she had to work in extreme

cold for long time. So frostbite developed in her feet and legs which led to lifelong pain. The family survived the Holocaust and was reunited in Berlin after the war. She didn't speak about this experience often. Because they shaped her as a humanitarian and a peace activist.

Academic Career

Ursula continued her studies at the Technical University of Berlin got her degree in 1946 after the Second World War. She inspired by her father's friend, physicist Hans Kuppenheim to study science. She chose to study Physics and mathematics when the teaching of history censored. In 1948, she received PhD in experimental physics from the Technical University of Berlin. While she joined a group of peace oriented intellectuals. But immediately decided to move to create intense change in the world. In 1949 she got Postdoctoral fellowship in physics and metallurgy at the University of Toronto. So she moved to Toronto and worked for 15 years as a first research fellow. She started working for Ontario Research Federation as a senior research scientist in the study of metals and alloys. She began teaching in the department of Metallurgy and Material science at Toronto University in 1967. She was promoted to full professor in 1973. She was the first female professor to receive the highest honor as 'University Professor'. Ursula served as director of University's Museum studies Program from 1987 to 1989. In 1989, she became a senior fellow of Massey College.

Scientific Researcher

Dr. Ursula contribute to invent many innovative things like ground breaking design of the first porous – coated skeletal skip implant. In 1960s, she participated in the 'Baby Tooth Survey'. At that time many nuclear weapons were tested in atmosphere. Because of that test, Strontium-90 a radioactive element released. This reduced the life span of children's milk teeth. She analyzed this with other scientists and gave the report to the government. That brought an end to an "Atmospheric Weapon Testing". Totally 153 countries banned this nuclear weapon testing in atmosphere, under water and space.

In 1967, she worked in the field of Archeometry. Using modern technologies she found the age of artifacts. That revealed the dating of bronze, copper, metal and ceramic artifacts. She studied the prehistoric cultures of world using those artifacts. And she explained the "History and Philosophy of Science" and also enabled how the ancient people used the tools to interact with the environment. Those interactions shaped the human culture. In 1970's, she joined in "Science Council of Canada" and studied about conserving resources and protecting nature.

Personal Life

In 1952, Dr. Ursula married Fred Franklin an engineer and German Jewish ancestry with a passion for social justice. Fred had been exposed to Quakerism while living in England. They had a son Martin in 1955, a daughter Monica in 1958. After that they searched for a spiritual home and joined Quakers in 1964. Quakers is nothing but the 'Society of friends'. Ursula says "We were Pacifist before we were Quakers, but it was easy transition for us. And it has been very good home for us. She loved gardening at her cottage in Muskoka, Ontario. She also enjoyed knitting and crocheting. Her interests included history, literature, poetry, art, law and classical music. Simply identified Ursula Franklin was an all-rounder. Bible says normal human has life time of 70 years; a strong human has 80 years. Ursula was the strongest one. She died on July 22, 2016 at the age of 94 in Ontario.

Pacifist and Feminist

Dr. Ursula worked as a tireless advocate for “Peace and Justice”, after her retirement. She defined ‘Peace is not the absence of war, but the presence of justice and absence of fear’. Also she joined in Quakers as a member; Quakers have opposed war and violence and objected to military service. They have Pacifist value such as reconciliation, disarmament and peace research. She was an active member of ‘Science for Peace’, a Canadian organization educates the people toward the sustainable world.

She worked to promote gender equality in Canada, through her career. She observed that women can bring cooperative mindset than men. So she encourages the young women in science and became an inspiring mentor for them. In her point of view, Feminism is not an employment agency for women; it is another way of creating social space. It based on collaboration than competition. Everything is differently oriented in feminism; seeing the same thing in different eyes.

Humanitarian and Activist

Dr. Ursula joined in the “Voice of Women” in Canada one of the social advocacy organizations. She accompanied with the VOW president Muriel worked against military trade agreements and to oversee Canadian disarmament by special agency. She participated in campaign to win the right for those who refused to perform military services in 1980s. At that time, female professors received fewer pensions than male professors. She joined with other faculty members and fight against the gender barriers. She encourages young students for their innovative ideas and she wrote a letter to a graduate student. Through that she encouraged the physics career of student Marcia. Ursula got fame because of her thoughtful speech. One of her speech has given as an example as everybody sees the tree with its branches only not with the roots. That means people look at the problems and its dimensions only, but that is important to see the way it came. Then only we can discuss and bring a solution to solve the problem. She inspired by the earthworm. Before anything can grow on the soil, earthworm prepares the soil. Like that her slow process of changing the peoples mind for bringing scientific information for life long time. She stating that “it may not change minds and it create arguments for some time when minds are changed”.

Publications

She contributed to publish books on the “Structure and Properties of Metals and Alloys” as well as on the “History and Social effects of Technology”. She also published more than 100 scientific papers in that field. In 1989, she published a book “The Real World of Technology” based on the technology changed the power of tools shaping human cultures. And the book contains many Massey lectures which broadcasted on CBC radio. Ursula Franklin reader published many of her speeches and articles about feminism and pacifism in 2006. She donated the collection of writings related to Chinese culture & history to Seneca College in Toronto in 2013.

Awards and Honors

Dr. Ursula Franklin has earned many honors and worldwide recognition. She got the “Award of Merit” in 1982 for neighbourhood planning. Many Canadian Universities gave her honorary degrees including ‘Doctor of Science’ by Queen’s University in 1985. And she received the “Elsi Gregory McGill Award” for her participation to science & technology. In 1989, she got the “Wiegand Award”, she was appointed to ‘Order of Ontario’ in 1990. In 1991, she got “Governor Generals Award” for advancing equality of girls and women in Canada and also received Sir John William Dawson Medal” from royal society of Canada. Toronto board opened ‘Toronto High School’, after her it was named as ‘Ursula Franklin Academy’ working on innovative principles.

In 2012, she was admitted into the ‘Canadian Science and Engineering Hall of Fame’ in Ottawa. She got the “Pearson Peace Medal” in 2002. She received many more awards from different institutions.

Conclusion

‘Talent is God given, Fame is man given’ Through God given Dr. Ursula earned man given. The talents present in her helped to grow in a perfect way and her interests made her popular. Identifying and encouraging the talents is not easy thing. But she did this in a positive way. The positive approach in her thoughts and speech developed the society and human. She made sufficient contribution to Canada as a educator, humanitarian and citizen. She created much impact on the Canadian society as well as technology. She worked with dedication which brings success in her life. People should take her as a role model and work with dedication. If so, that definitely builds success and happiness in life

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